

The Absolute Predictor: An SVM-Driven Paradigm for 100% Accurate Diabetes Insight

Ransford Ganyo
University of Cape Coast, Ghana

Benedict Nii Ayi Armah
University of Ghana, Ghana

Peter Paul Issah
Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana

November 27, 2024

Abstract

This study presents the development of a Support Vector Machine (*SVM*) model for predicting diabetes using various clinical features. The dataset underwent preprocessing and feature selection to enhance model performance. The evaluation of the model's accuracy was conducted through a confusion matrix, which revealed a perfect classification rate of 100%. Additionally, the analysis included Partial Dependence Plots illustrating the relationship between Body Mass Index (*BMI*) and predicted diabetes, as well as square plots depicting True Positive Rates (*TPR*), False Negative Rates (*FNR*), Positive Predictive Values (*PPV*), and False Discovery Rates (*FDR*). The results highlighted glucose levels, *BMI*, and age as the most significant predictors of diabetes. This research underscores the potential of machine learning models like SVM in improving early detection and intervention strategies for diabetes management, providing valuable insights into clinical decision-making processes.

1 Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by high blood glucose levels, resulting from either insufficient insulin production or the body's inability to effectively use the insulin it produces [9]. The prevalence of diabetes has been increasing globally, with significant implications for public health [5]. Early detection and management of diabetes are crucial for preventing serious complications, such as cardiovascular diseases, neuropathy, and kidney failure [6].

Machine learning (*ML*) models have become increasingly important in the field of medical diagnostics, offering tools that can analyze complex datasets to identify patterns and predict outcomes with high accuracy [10]. Among these models, Support Vector Machines (*SVM*) are particularly well-suited for binary classification problems, such as predicting the presence or absence of a disease [7]. This study applies an *SVM* model to predict diabetes using clinical data, aiming to provide insights into the most significant predictors of the disease.

2 Methodology

The dataset used in this study was obtained from Bibieni Hospital in the Ashanti Region. It consists of various clinical features of patients, such as age, *BMI*, blood pressure, glucose levels, and more. The preprocessing of the dataset involved handling missing values, encoding categorical variables, and normalizing continuous variables.

2.1 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is a critical step in machine learning, particularly in healthcare, where data quality can vary significantly [11]. Missing data were handled using mean imputation for continuous variables and mode imputation for categorical variables. Categorical variables were converted to numerical values using one-hot encoding, which allows the *SVM* model to process the data effectively.

2.2 Feature Selection

Feature selection is a critical step in model development, aimed at identifying the most relevant features that enhance the predictive power of the model. In this study, feature selection was conducted using a combination of domain knowledge and statistical methods. Specifically, we employed the chi-square test for categorical variables and Analysis of Variance (*ANOVA*) for continuous variables [4]. These statistical tests facilitated the identification of features with the highest correlation to the outcome variable—diabetes diagnosis. The selected features were subsequently used to train the final *SVM* model, ensuring that only those variables contributing significantly to prediction accuracy were included. This revision maintains a formal tone and clearly outlines the methodology used for feature selection in your study, emphasizing its importance in enhancing model performance.

2.3 Model Training

The dataset was partitioned into training and testing sets, with 70% allocated for training and 30% for testing purposes. A linear Support Vector Machine (*SVM*) model was subsequently trained using the selected features, employing a linear kernel, which is well-suited for binary classification tasks. The training process included hyperparameter optimization through cross-validation to

enhance the model’s robustness and generalizability [8]. This approach ensured that the model was adequately tuned to minimize overfitting while maximizing predictive performance. This revision maintains clarity and formality, effectively reflecting the methodology used in your study.

3 Results

3.1 Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix is a fundamental evaluation metric for classification models, providing a detailed breakdown of the model’s performance by showing the number of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives.

The confusion matrix obtained from this study indicates that the *SVM* model achieved perfect classification on the test data, correctly identifying all cases of diabetes and non-diabetes. This is depicted in Figure 1 and 2, which shows a 100% accuracy rate. However, it is important to note that perfect accuracy in small datasets may not generalize well to larger, more diverse datasets [15]. While a perfect confusion matrix might seem ideal, it can sometimes indicate overfitting, especially if the model is too complex or if the data is limited. The model might perform very well on the training data but might not generalize as well to new, unseen data.

3.2 True Positive Rates and False Negative Rates

To assess the performance of the Support Vector Machine (*SVM*) model in predicting diabetes, we analyzed the True Positive Rate (*TPR*) and False Negative Rate (*FNR*). These metrics are critical for evaluating the model’s effectiveness in accurately identifying positive cases of diabetes while minimizing misclassifications. True Positive Rate (*TPR*) also referred to as sensitivity or recall, quantifies the proportion of actual positive cases that are correctly identified by the model. It is mathematically defined as:

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

where *TP* represents true positives and *FN* represents false negatives.

False Negative Rate (*FNR*) reflects the proportion of actual positives that are incorrectly classified as negatives. It is calculated as:

$$FNR = \frac{FN}{TP + FN} = 1 - TPR$$

Figure 1 illustrates the TPR and FNR for the *SVM* model, with percentages clearly indicated. It represents a distinct classification outcome, providing a visual summary of the model’s performance.

Figure 1 displays two diagrams: one representing the Confusion Matrix and the other consisting of the True Positive Rate and the False Negative Rate.

The TPR is indicated at 100%, signifying that all actual diabetes cases were accurately identified by the model. Conversely, the FNR is shown at 0%, demonstrating that no actual diabetes cases were misclassified as negative. As illustrated in Figure 1, the SVM model achieved perfect classification performance: True Positive Rate: The TPR at 100% indicates that every patient diagnosed with diabetes was correctly identified by the model. This level of sensitivity is essential in clinical settings, where failing to identify a diabetes diagnosis can lead to severe health consequences [12]. False Negative Rate: The FNR at 0% signifies that there were no missed diagnoses among actual diabetes cases. Maintaining a low FNR is critical to ensure that patients receive timely interventions, thereby reducing potential complications associated with undiagnosed diabetes [2]. Clinical Implications: Understanding TPR and FNR is vital for evaluating diagnostic tests in healthcare. A high TPR ensures that most patients with diabetes are correctly identified, which is crucial for timely treatment. Conversely, minimizing false negatives is essential to avoid overlooking cases that necessitate intervention. The insights gained from this analysis can guide clinicians in selecting appropriate thresholds based on clinical needs and patient populations. Conclusion The results highlight the model's effectiveness in achieving high sensitivity while maintaining low rates of missed diagnoses. This dual focus on TPR and FNR underscores the importance of careful threshold selection in clinical practice to optimize patient outcomes.

Figure 1: True Positive Rates and False Negative Rates for SVM Model

3.3 Positive Predictive Values and False Discovery Rates

To further evaluate the performance of the Support Vector Machine (*SVM*) model in predicting diabetes, we analyzed the Positive Predictive Value (*PPV*) and False Discovery Rate (*FDR*). These metrics are essential for understanding the reliability of positive predictions made by the model. Positive Predictive Value (*PPV*), also known as precision, measures the proportion of true positive results in all positive predictions made by the model. It is calculated as:

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

where

TP represents true positives and *FP* represents false positives. False Discovery Rate (*FDR*) indicates the proportion of false positives among all positive predictions. It is calculated as:

$$FDR = \frac{FP}{TP + FP} = 1 - PPV$$

Figure 2 illustrates the *PPV* and *FDR* for the *SVM* model, with percentages clearly indicated. Each represents a distinct classification outcome, providing a visual summary of the model's performance.

Figure 2 displays two diagrams: one representing the Confusion Matrix and the other representing Positive Predictive Value with False Discovery Rate. The *PPV* is indicated at 100%, signifying that all positive predictions made by the model were correct. Conversely, the *FDR* is shown at 0%, demonstrating that there were no false positives in the predictions.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the *SVM* model achieved perfect classification performance: Positive Predictive Value: The *PPV* at 100% indicates that every positive prediction made by the model corresponds to an actual case of diabetes. This level of precision is crucial in clinical settings, where accurate identification of positive cases is necessary to avoid unnecessary interventions [16]. False Discovery Rate: The *FDR* at 0% signifies that there were no false positives among the positive predictions. A low *FDR* is essential to ensure that patients are not incorrectly diagnosed, which could lead to inappropriate treatment or anxiety [13].

Understanding *PPV* and *FDR* is vital for evaluating diagnostic tests in healthcare. A high *PPV* ensures that most patients identified as having diabetes truly have the condition, which is essential for effective patient management. Conversely, minimizing false discoveries is crucial to avoid unnecessary interventions and healthcare costs. The insights gained from this analysis can guide clinicians in making informed decisions regarding diagnosis and treatment strategies. Analyzing Positive Predictive Values and False Discovery Rates provides a comprehensive view of the *SVM* model's performance in predicting diabetes. The results highlight the model's effectiveness in achieving high precision while maintaining low rates of false positives. This dual focus on *PPV* and *FDR* underscores the importance of careful evaluation metrics in clinical practice to optimize patient outcomes.

Figure 2: Positive Predictive Value and False Discovery Rate for SVM Model

3.4 Feature Importance of SVM Model

Understanding the importance of each feature in the *SVM* model is crucial for interpreting the model's predictions. Feature importance in *SVM* is derived from the absolute values of the model coefficients, which represent the weight assigned to each feature in the decision boundary.

Figure 3 illustrates the relative importance of each feature used in the *SVM* model. Features with higher importance scores, such as glucose levels and *BMI*, were found to be more predictive of diabetes, aligning with existing medical literature [1]. This analysis highlights the critical factors that contribute to diabetes risk, providing valuable information for healthcare professionals.

Figure 3: Feature Importance for SVM Model

3.5 Partial Dependence Plot for Body Mass Index

To elucidate the relationship between Body Mass Index (BMI) and the predicted probability of diabetes, a Partial Dependence Plot (PDP) was generated. The PDP serves as a valuable visualization tool that illustrates how the predicted outcome varies with changes in a specific feature while accounting for the average effects of all other features in the model [3]. Figure 4 depicts the Partial Dependence Plot for BMI in relation to diabetes predictions. The plot features two distinct lines: one representing the probability of a "Yes" prediction (indicating diabetes) and another representing a "No" prediction (indicating no diabetes). The analysis of the plot reveals a clear trend: as BMI increases, the likelihood of a positive diabetes diagnosis (Yes) rises, while the probability of a negative diagnosis (No) declines. This inverse relationship is visually represented by the two intersecting lines: Yes Prediction Line: This line exhibits an upward trajectory as BMI values increase, suggesting that higher BMI levels are associated with an increased risk of diabetes. This finding aligns with existing literature that identifies obesity as a significant risk factor for developing diabetes [14]. No Prediction Line: In contrast, this line trends downward with increasing BMI , indicating that higher BMI values correlate with a decreased likelihood of not having diabetes.

4 Discussion

The findings of this study underscore the effectiveness of the Support Vector Machine (SVM) model in predicting diabetes with high accuracy. The results, as demonstrated by the confusion matrix, indicate that the model achieved

Figure 4: Partial Dependence Plot for Body Mass Index Against Predicted Diabetes

perfect classification on the test dataset, highlighting its potential utility as a diagnostic tool. The feature importance analysis provided valuable insights into the clinical variables that significantly influence diabetes prediction. Specifically, glucose levels, Body Mass Index (BMI), and age emerged as the most critical predictors, which aligns with established risk factors for diabetes. These findings can assist clinicians in focusing their assessments on these relevant factors when evaluating diabetes risk in patients. Despite these promising results, this study is not without limitations. The relatively small dataset used necessitates caution in interpreting the model’s performance; thus, validation on larger and more heterogeneous populations is warranted. Furthermore, while a linear *SVM* model was employed in this analysis, exploring non-linear models or ensemble methods may yield improved performance and should be considered for future research.

5 Conclusion

This study successfully applied a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model to predict diabetes using clinical features, achieving high accuracy in classification. The analysis of feature importance provided a deeper understanding of the model’s decision-making process and highlighted the most critical factors in diabetes prediction. These findings have important implications for the early detection and management of diabetes.

Future work should focus on validating the model on larger datasets, exploring the use of non-linear SVM models, and integrating additional clinical features that may improve prediction accuracy. The integration of machine learning models like SVM into clinical practice has the potential to significantly enhance the early diagnosis and management of chronic diseases such as diabetes.

References

- [1] Eric Adua et al. “Predictive model and feature importance for early detection of type II diabetes mellitus”. In: *Translational Medicine Communications* 6 (2021), pp. 1–15.
- [2] Josie Carmichael et al. “Advances in screening, early diagnosis and accurate staging of diabetic neuropathy”. In: *Frontiers in endocrinology* 12 (2021), p. 671257.
- [3] Brandon M Greenwell et al. “pdp: An R package for constructing partial dependence plots.” In: *R J.* 9.1 (2017), p. 421.
- [4] Seung Won Lee et al. “Methods for testing statistical differences between groups in medical research: statistical standard and guideline of Life Cycle Committee”. In: *Life Cycle* 2 (2022).
- [5] Jinli Liu et al. “Trends in the incidence of diabetes mellitus: results from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017 and implications for diabetes mellitus prevention”. In: *BMC public health* 20 (2020), pp. 1–12.
- [6] Sally M Marshall and Allan Flyvbjerg. “Prevention and early detection of vascular complications of diabetes”. In: *Bmj* 333.7566 (2006), pp. 475–480.
- [7] Florian Mittag et al. “Use of support vector machines for disease risk prediction in genome-wide association studies: Concerns and opportunities”. In: *Human mutation* 33.12 (2012), pp. 1708–1718.
- [8] Giorgos Mountrakis, Jungho Im, and Caesar Ogole. “Support vector machines in remote sensing: A review”. In: *ISPRS journal of photogrammetry and remote sensing* 66.3 (2011), pp. 247–259.
- [9] Y Mukhtar, A Galalain, and Ujej Yunusa. “A modern overview on diabetes mellitus: a chronic endocrine disorder”. In: *European Journal of Biology* 5.2 (2020), pp. 1–14.
- [10] Amir Masoud Rahmani et al. “Machine learning (ML) in medicine: Review, applications, and challenges”. In: *Mathematics* 9.22 (2021), p. 2970.
- [11] Eka Sabna, Zupri Henra Hartomi, and Yayang Sahira. “Analyzes Health Data By Applying Data Science For Students in The Undergraduate Study Program in Public Health Faculty of Health Hang Tuah University Pekanbaru”. In: *RECORD: Journal of Loyalty and Community Development* 1.1 (2024), pp. 55–62.

- [12] David B Sacks et al. “Guidelines and recommendations for laboratory analysis in the diagnosis and management of diabetes mellitus”. In: *Clinical chemistry* 57.6 (2011), e1–e47.
- [13] Imran Mohammed Sajid, Kathleen Frost, and Ash K Paul. “‘Diagnostic downshift’: clinical and system consequences of extrapolating secondary care testing tactics to primary care”. In: *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine* 27.3 (2022), pp. 141–148.
- [14] André J Scheen. “From obesity to diabetes: why, when and who?” In: *Acta clinica belgica* 55.1 (2000), pp. 9–15.
- [15] Ludwig Schmidt et al. “Adversarially robust generalization requires more data”. In: *Advances in neural information processing systems* 31 (2018).
- [16] Robert Trevethan. “Sensitivity, specificity, and predictive values: foundations, pliabilitys, and pitfalls in research and practice”. In: *Frontiers in public health* 5 (2017), p. 307.